

Important Skills to work on Prior and after Graduating from your Program:

1. How to do a search on various database using boolean search skills.
2. How to search and systematic screen the works of literature to get the right papers you planned to search for by using your keywords.
3. Skills on how to critique an article.
4. Understanding the scholarly importance of a good literature review and its applicability to your career.
5. Understanding the various forms of literature review and the procedures on how to do them. Especially, systematic literature review.
6. How to read, summarize, compare, synthesize, analyse an article.
7. How to write an article in a scholarly way with emphasis on grammar, logic, structure, design, context, content, ethics, and others. Scholarly writing is a great asset.
8. Learning about the various kinds of research approach and the proper way to conduct a study with emphasis on credibility, reliability, validity, generalisation, and others.
9. Proper and ethical way of data collection, processing, analysing, and write ups.
10. Learn couple of research methodologies, its ethics and way of application to your work and the world around you.
11. Learning a new advance software(s) in your field is a plus for future progression.
12. Others you will learn along the way from your supervisor, colleagues, collaborations, and others.

PS: Kindly, probe more and share what you learn with me and others.

"PRACTICE, PRACTICE, PRACTICE" concept taught to me by four wonderful Professors, thus, Prof. Luo Wenping, Prof. Jim Phillips, Prof. Zheng Shiyuan, and Assist. Prof. Seth K. Baffoe.

"The future is as bright as your FAITH" by: President Thomas S. Monson.

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Be of good cheer and go for your dream.